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Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND) and Development of Tertiary Education in Nigeria: A Study of Federal Tertiary Educational Institutions in Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the effect of TETFund's interventions on tertiary education development, using federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra State, Nigeria, as the study area. But specifically, it investigated the effect of academic staff training and development, instructional materials and equipment, research and publications, library collections development and physical infrastructure development on tertiary education development. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The study identified two populations which are the academic staff and the students' leadership across the institutions under investigation namely, Nnamdi Azikiwe University Awka, Federal Polytechnic Oko and Federal College of Education (Technical) Umuanze. For the academic staff, the population consists of 4,427 teaching staff, 1239 was identified across the institutions. A sample size of 850 was determined for the academic staff using Borg and Gall approach and for the students' leadership, 302, was determined through the application of Taro Yameni's statistical formula for determining sample size from a finite population. Major statistical tools of analysis include summary statistics of percentages and frequency tables which are in the ranks of descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation coefficient and multiple regression analysis. Major findings suggest that TETFund's intervention on academic staff training and development, provision of instructional materials and equipment, support for research and publications, library collections development as well as physical infrastructure development have significant and positive effect on the development of tertiary educational institutions located in Anambra State. The study concluded that TETFund intervention has contributed in no less measures to the development of tertiary education in Nigeria, The study recommended that TETFund should continue to provide funding support for tertiary education development in Nigeria with a focus on academic staff training and development, provision of instructional materials and equipment, research and publication, library collections development as well as physical infrastructure development.

Keywords: Tertiary Education Trust Fund, Development of Tertiary Education, Federal Tertiary Educational Institutions

INTRODUCTION

The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) was originally established as Education Trust Fund (ETF) by the Act No. 7 of 1993 as amended by the Act No. 40 of 1998 (now replaced with the Tertiary Education Trust Fund Act 2011). The Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) was the architect of TETFund which started as Education Trust Fund (ETF) as noted above. From the late 1980s, poor funding of the educational sector in Nigeria led to decay and deterioration of all tiers of education. Facilities had almost collapsed, teachers and lecturers' morale was at its lowest ebb. Enabling environment for conducive teaching and learning had become totally absent. ASUU's constant engagement with the then administration of Ibrahim Babangida led to the constitution of the Grey Longe Commission on the Review of Higher Education in Nigeria in December 1990 by the Federal Government. The Grey Longe Commission recommended among others the funding of higher education through earmarked tax to be borne by companies operating in Nigeria.

Consequently, an implementation committee under the chairmanship of Professor Olu O. Akinkugbe was constituted to implement the Grey Longe Commission report's recommendations. Furthermore, an agreement was signed between the Federal Government and ASUU on the 3rd of September, 1992 on funding of universities. In January 1993, the Education Tax Act No. 7 of 1993 was promulgated alongside other education-related Decrees. The Decree specifically imposed a 2% tax on the assessable profits of all companies operating in Nigeria. The move was acknowledged as a home-grown solution meant for addressing all issues of funding with regard to rehabilitating the decaying infrastructure, restore of the lost glory of education and confidence in the system as well as to consolidate the gains thereto; build the capacity of teachers and lecturers; teachers' development; development of prototype designs; etc. The Education Tax Act No. 7 of 1993 mandated the Fund to operate as an intervention Fund to all levels of public education in Nigeria (Federal, State and Local). This mandate was faithfully discharged between 1993 and May 2011 when the ETF Act was repelled and replaced with the Tertiary Education Trust Fund Act, due to lapses and challenges in operating the Education Trust Fund. These lapses and challenges include:

1. The ETF was overburdened and, overstretched and as such, it could only render palliative support to all levels of public educational institutions in Nigeria.
2. Duplication of functions and mandate of other agencies set up after the ETF such as Universal Basic Education (UBE) and Millennium Development Goals (MDGs).
3. The decay, rot and dilapidation of facilities in the tertiary education continued to be irritating as funds were only thinly spread (Andrews and Amah, 2020).

So, Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) is a direct response to the agitation for reforms and proper funding of the deteriorating educational infrastructure and falling standards at all levels in the sector. It is indeed an intervention agency established to provide supplementary support to all levels of funding in public tertiary educational institutions with the main purpose of using funding alongside project management for the rehabilitation, restoration and consideration of tertiary education in Nigeria (FGN, 2011). According to Dan (2015), the scope of disbursing the two percent education tax deduction is that 41 percent of the fund realized should go to the universities, 30 percent to the Polytechnics and 29 percent to the Colleges of education for the purposes of developing physical infrastructures, purchase and installation of vital equipment, development of library, academic staff training and development, research and publication and any other need as may be considered necessary by the Board of Trustees (Anorue & Ikedigwe, 2021). The Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) is empowered to assess and collect the education Tax. The mandate of the Fund as provided in section 7(1)(a) to (e) of the TETFund Act, 2011, is to administer and disburse the amount in the fund to target institutions which are universities, polytechnics and colleges of education that are owned by the Federal and State governments (Anorue & Ikedigwe, 2021).

Tertiary education development encompasses many things and they include but not limited to: development of physical infrastructure, purchase, installation and maintenance of relevant instructional materials and equipment for teaching and learning, academic staff training and development. It

includes also improvement in research and publication and provision of library facilities, improved supply of electricity and water within the educational institutions. They are planned activities which are geared towards making the teaching and learning environment as conducive as possible (Usman, 2014). In particular, research and publications are important components of tertiary education development. In fact, Lucky and Samson (2018) note that advancement in research gives rise to growth in science and technology which in turn leads to industrialization, employment opportunities, increase in production of goods, services and income, creation of wealth and improved quality of life. Unfortunately, inadequate funding in the tertiary education sector, in particular has led to serious brain drain syndrome which has continued unabated. It is a situation where the best brains in their good numbers, migrate to other countries where their services can be better appreciated. It is a situation which has badly affected the quality of teaching, learning and research in the Nigeria's tertiary education system (Onwuchekwa, 2016). There has been public outcry against government's poor budgetary allocation to the educational sector and ASUU, in particular have engaged the government severally on the issue of underfunding, but as it would appear, it does not seem as if much has been achieved. On the contrary, the decay and deterioration has continued to threaten the foundations of tertiary education in the country.

From the above, there is no doubt that TETFund's cardinal objective is to generate additional funds to support tertiary education in Nigeria to avoid an ugly situation of total collapse. In the light of the above, this study intends to examine the effect of TETFund on tertiary education development in Nigeria with respect to intervention in the areas of academic staff training and development, provision of instructional materials and equipment, research and publication, physical infrastructure development as well as library collection development through the provision of relevant library materials. The study hopes to use the federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra State; which are Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka; Federal Polytechnic Oko and Federal College of Education (Technical), Umuze as the study area.

Statement of the Problem

The underfunding of the educational sector brought about decay, dilapidation and deterioration in tertiary education in Nigeria from the late 1980s. There is sufficient evidence to show that the rate of deterioration has continued unabated and that infact, it has become alarming thereby leading to fallen standards in the system as the best brains started migrating to other countries where their services can be better appreciated. The brain-drain syndrome which has continued uptill today has done unimaginable damage to the quality of teaching and learning as well as research in the Nigeria's tertiary education system (Onwuchekwa, 2016). There have been public outcry against government's poor budgetary allocations to the educational sector generally from different quarters and ASUU, in particular on several occasions have engaged and are still engaging the government on the issues of underfunding of the educational sector, but it appears that nothing much have been achieved except for the establishment of the Tertiary Education Trust Fund TETFund which was created to raise and disburse supplementary funding for the public tertiary educational institutions in the country as an intervention agency. However, past studies in this area have presented conflicting results concerning the effect of TETFund on tertiary education development in Nigeria whereas some studies' results (Ogunode, 2023; Andrews and Amah, 2020; Ezekwe and Ani, 2023; Yakubu, Bellow, Yahya and Adamu, 2022) showed that TETFund intervention in tertiary education has brought about significant improvement in the sector, a few others (Wenibowel &Warrant, 2021; Nagbi and Micah; Onwuchekwa, 2016) were of the opinion that TETFund intervention has not been significant, especially in the areas of academic staff training and development as well as research and publications. Nevertheless, a look at the institutions where TETFund have made interventions across the nation reveals that the agency have actually made some reasonable level of impact, especially in the area of physical infrastructure development even in the face of huge allegations of corrupt practices during project implementation after TETFund might have disbursed the funds to the benefiting institutions. At the same time, there have equally been issues of abscondment, that is, the teaching staff sent overseas

for further studies or conferences on TETFund sponsorship refusing to return to the country to contribute to the development of the sector after they might have received the training. Consequently, the study has become necessary to investigate the effect of the fund on public tertiary educational institutions in Nigeria, using the federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra State as the study area in addition to mediating among the conflicting results on the effect of TETFund on tertiary education development in Nigeria.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

TETFund

The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) was established as an intervention agency under the TETFund Act – Tertiary Education Trust Fund (Establishment, etc) Act, 2011; charged with the responsibility of managing, disbursing and monitoring the education tax to public tertiary institutions in Nigeria. To enable TETFund achieve the above objectives, TETFund Act, 2011 imposed a 2% Education tax on assessable profit of all registered companies in Nigeria. The Federal Inland Revenue Services (FIRS) was empowered by the Act to assess and collect the Education Tax (Nagbi & Micah, 2019). According to them, the Fund administers the tax imposed by the Act and disburses the amount collected to public tertiary educational institutions only. It also monitors the projects executed with the funds allocated to the beneficiaries. Therefore, the TETFund was conceptualized as an intervention Fund to bring about improvement to all aspects of tertiary education in Nigeria to ensure that the high quality standards of higher education in the country returns (Akamolafe and Belo, 2019).

Tertiary Education

Tertiary education refers to all formal post-secondary education, including public and private universities, polytechnics, colleges of education, technical training institutes and vocational schools. Tertiary education is instrumental in fostering growth, reducing unemployment and poverty rates as well as boosting shared prosperity (World Bank, 2017). To the organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD, 2020), tertiary education refers to post-secondary education which encompasses all forms of education and training that occur after secondary education, including academic, vocational and technical programme. In the same vein, the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO, 2020), defines tertiary education as the educational programs that lead to the award of degrees, diplomas, certificates or other qualifications at the post-secondary level, including universities, colleges, polytechnics and other institutions. In a related development, the World Bank (2018) defines tertiary education as the stage of education that follows secondary education, providing students with advanced knowledge, skills and competencies in specific fields, preparing them for the labour market or further education.

Tertiary Education Development

Tertiary education development refers to so many things which are aimed at improving tertiary education in all aspects, the ease of teaching and learning, the overall standard in the system and the quality of graduates being produced from the system. Apparently, poor or less developed educational system cannot produce the type of graduates that can adequately compete with others on a global level. But before we move further into what constitutes tertiary education development in the Nigeria's context, let us look at how some scholars have conceptualized tertiary education in itself. Nwokolo (2008) cited in Ojong, Bessong and Ejue (2016) sees tertiary education as that education that is capable of producing Nigerians who can manufacture raw materials, machines and tools needed for our industries, produce enough food for local and international markets, invent new designs, discover drugs capable of curing diseases hitherto incurable and transform the nation from consuming one to a producing one.

To Okoro and Okey (2012), tertiary education is a social process which brings awareness, nurtures productive abilities and confers honour on the people as they venture to live useful purposeful lives in a dynamic society. But according to FRN (2004), tertiary education is the education given after

secondary education in universities, polytechnics, monotecnics, colleges of education, including those institutions offering correspondence courses. World Bank (2002) maintains that in today's life learning framework, tertiary education provides not only high level skills necessary for every market but also the training that is essential for professionalism in all spheres of human endeavor. However, in summary, tertiary education is that education which leads people to the realization of the potentials of each to contribute maximally to the development of oneself and the community. Ivowi (2006) notes that knowledge and skills acquired through exposure to relevant programmes in tertiary institutions, manifest in their innovative and creative use to increase the tempo, quantity and quality of goods and services in the society.

Iyamu and Kumo (2020) added that tertiary education development equally means producing persons equipped with appropriate values, thinking, creative and innovative ability and sound knowledge of how the economy can be made to function and grow. In their opinion, one of the major roles of tertiary education as a driver and propeller of the economy is to produce a production-oriented rather than a consumption-oriented citizenry. But can this be said to be true of tertiary education in Nigeria? In more organized and responsible societies, tertiary education is acknowledged and respected as the engine house for research and innovations which are fundamental to social and economic transformations. Responsible and informed governments look up to tertiary institutions for empirically based ideas to support policies rather than base such policies on common sense or political consideration as mostly observed in Nigeria. Governments in organized societies fund tertiary institutions to carry out research on national priorities such as security, warfare, health, agriculture, etc, as part of tertiary education development. Until tertiary education in Nigeria starts to produce graduates with creative abilities which will enable them to possess requisite skills or life support skill, it cannot be said to be developing.

Theoretical Framework

This study reviewed two theories in the related field, namely, the principal-Agent and The Human Capital Theories. Jensen and Mackling were believed to have developed the Principal-Agent Theory in 1976 to help in explaining and understanding the relationship between the principal on one hand and the Agent on the other hand, under the contractual bond aimed at achieving success for both parties. However, the theory has evolved to address newer concerns in institutional behaviours between the principal and the Agent. The Principal-Agent model theorizes that principal and agent believe on whether they are at risk or not, the perception of the benefits of taking action supersedes. This influences their readiness to take action on what to do to achieve the desired organizational goals (Kiristo, 2008).

The principal-Agent Theory looks at the relationship in a contractual form between one or more individuals called the "principals", that employed another individual called the "agent" to execute some services on their behalf, which involves allocation of some resources to solve some problems and also delegates some powers and authority to the agent to act on behalf of the principal(s). According to Ahmad, Farley and Naidoo (2012), the principal-agency theory has been established by many researchers as one of the fundamental answers to the problems surrounding financing of higher education in high institutions in Nigeria. It has been found to be effective in explaining the relationship between the principal (Government) and the agent (higher educational institutions) in solving the perennial problem of higher education financing. Complementing the above postulation, Lane and Kiristo (2008) opine that the theory has a wide acceptance and adoption in explaining higher education financing. It is a known fact in this contemporary world that higher educational institutions (HEIs) are motivated by both economic and political motives to succeed. Connecting the theory to higher education finances, it tries to look at the relationship between the principal and the agent, and whether the agent adheres to the agreement by taking the required steps and procedure to achieve the desired results as expected by the principal. The contractual agreement between the two parties is built around the assumption that the agent has all the required competences and capabilities to carry out the task assigned and in the end yield better results for the principal.

The change paradigm of financing education in general and in particular, the higher education in the contemporary competitive market setting has increased the demand for prudence and financial transparency in utilizing and managing the limited public funds. Indeed, the principal-agent theory has the capacity and strength to offer solutions and it has been found to be a fundamental theory for research in principal-agency dynamics. The theory is absolutely in a good position to be applied to study the relationship between “government” (principal) and “higher education institutions” (agent). It is very apt in explaining how the government should provide some funds to HEIs to help or enable them perform the functions of producing quality manpower to manage the economy to create job opportunities for the unemployed, effectively render community service and carry out ground breaking researches through which development is attained in any country.

Looking at it in Nigerian context where more than 90 percent of the funds for HEIs come from the government/proprietor, it is necessary to monitor and checkmate the activities of the agent (i.e, the institutions). The theory is used to explain the sources of funds to the institutions of higher learning, which means whether there is a single or double principal, the framework explains whether the financial resources provided by the government (principal) to HEIs (agency) are adequate when measured by the benchmark given by the regulatory bodies of HEIs and by extension, the Ministry of Education.

Empirical Review

In a study conducted by Jumane, Ibrahim and Sabon Sara (2019) on impact of TETFund on staff training and development of institution in North West, Nigeria, descriptive survey design was used and out of 1241 lecturers, a sample of 423 was determined for the study. Findings from data analysis showed that TETFund intervention on staff training and development has led to acquisition of higher degrees by many staff of the tertiary institutions in the North West, Nigeria. The study concludes that TETFund’s support on conference attendance enabled staff to learn and update their skills, knowledge and understanding. In a related study, Yakubu, Bello, Yahaya and Adamu (2022) did an appraisal of the perception of staff in TETFund intervention in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State, Nigeria. In carrying out the research, survey method was adopted and findings suggest that TETFund’s intervention had positive and significant impact on academic staff training and development in Federal College of Education, Yola and Adamawa State Polytechnic, Yola. The study concludes that TETFund’s intervention has assisted the academic staff in the areas of training and development, physical infrastructure, modern facilities and academic research programmes in the institutions studied.

Ezekwe and Ani (2023) examined the effect of TETFund interventions on academic staff training in Nigerian universities. The study adopted Ex-post facto research design. Annual time series data obtained from secondary sources were used. Results from the analysis revealed that there is significant impact of TETFund intervention in academic staff training and development, which has impacted substantially academics’ teaching in South East public universities at ($P < 0.01$). It was also revealed that TETFund intervention in human capacity building has positive impact on the competence of academic staff of the benefiting institutions studied. The study concludes therefore that academic staff are likely to acquire more knowledge and skills and the capacity to face teaching and research competitively. Isiaka, Nasiru and Olushola (2020) carried out a study of TETFund’s intervention on academic staff’s capacity building in Lagos State University, Nigeria. The study utilized descriptive survey design as the method. Results of data analysis revealed that provision of instructional materials for effective teaching and learning is the major priority of the intervention. The results showed also that provision of instructional materials and equipment were positively and strongly correlated with improved performance among the academics in the university. The study concludes that TETFund intervention has significantly impacted tertiary education development in the university as the students are now better off.

Okolo, Adadu, Umma and Yamma (2021) did a study on TETFund and physical infrastructure development in tertiary institutions in Bauchi State, Nigeria, using Bauchi State Polytechnic as the study area. The study made use of descriptive survey design. Data analysis revealed that the state of physical infrastructure in the institution before the intervention of TETFund were inadequate and dysfunctional. It showed too that TETFund's intervention has addressed substantially the infrastructural gap in the institution. The study concludes that strengthening of TETFund as an intervention agency will provide more benefits to the ailing tertiary institutions across the Nigerian nation. Onwuchekwa (2016) conducted a study on influence of TETFund on educational research in Nigerian universities. The study adopted descriptive survey design. From a population of 6939 lecturers in South East universities, a sample size of 386 was determined. Results of the analysis showed that TETFund intervention had no significant influence on educational research of the lecturers in the selected universities. The study concludes that the intervention in the universities in the area of research sponsorship was so small that it's influence was insignificant.

Ananyi and Onyekwere (2024) conducted a study on Tetfund and the transformation of higher education in Nigeria. The study adopted qualitative research method, using content analysis. The results showed that Tetfund contribution to tertiary education development in Nigeria is significant. It was concluded that Tetfund has been acting as a catalyst for academic recovery and excellence since inception. Anachuna, Oguejiofor, Agu and Itoya (2024) investigated the impact of tertiary education trust fund intervention on research development for effective management of federal universities in South East, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey design. Result of the analysis showed that Tetfund intervention had a significant impact on research development for effective management of federal universities in South-East, Nigeria. The study concludes that Tetfund has improved the lots of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Udu (2024) did a study tertiary education trust fund interventions and sustainable development in Nigerian universities, using Ebonyi State University, Abakaliki. The study adopted content analysis. It was found that Tetfund interventions in Nigerian universities, particularly Ebonyi State University have impacted positively on the infrastructural and human development of the institutions; the implications of this for sustainable development is also positive. The study concludes that Tetfund intervention has become the major sustenance of tertiary education in Nigeria.

Isaac, Steve and Okpe (2024) examined the impact of tertiary education Trustfund (Tetfund) on academic staff development to all benefiting tertiary institutions in Benue State of Nigeria. The study made use of descriptive survey design. Result from the data analysis showed that there is a positive and strong relationship between Tetfund's intervention and academic staff training and development of the academic staff of the Benue State University. Also, there is a positive and strong relationship between Tetfund's intervention and academic staff research outputs in tertiary institutions in Benue State. The study concludes that Tetfund should increase the current amount allocated for academic staff training considering the present economic conditions and remove or reduce the bureaucratic processes involved in accessing the funds to ensure greater impact.

Mac-Ozigbo, Ama, Ifegwu and Igbokwe-Ibeto (2024) conducted a study on Tetfund's intervention on academic staff training and development in selected federal universities in Nigeria, 2018 – 2022. The study made use of descriptive survey design. Major tool of analysis were correlation coefficients through the application of SPSS version 20.0. Findings of the study showed that Tetfund sponsorship of research has significant positive impact on academic staff development. It established further that Tetfund overseas sponsorship for staff development has significant positive impact on performance of the beneficiaries. The study concludes that Tetfund has succeeded in prioritizing academic staff training and development as well as research and publications in tertiary institutions across the nation.

Shuaibu and Abuhuraira (2024) did an evaluation study on the role of Tetfund in improving infrastructure and library facilities in Northwest, Nigerian universities. Survey research design was adopted for the study. Results of the data analysis through SPSS showed that there is significant positive effect of Tetfund intervention on infrastructural development and provision of library facilities in the Northwest universities, Nigeria. The study concludes that Tetfund is playing a key role in the

development of tertiary education in the Northwest zone of Nigeria. Omosidi, Atolagbe and Johnson (2023) conducted a study on the impact of interventions from Tetfund on productivity of lecturers in Kogi State colleges of education, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey design as its method. Results of data analysis showed that Tetfund has done considerably well by having moderate interventions on staff training and development, research publications instructional materials and equipment as well as physical infrastructure. The study concludes that such levels of intervention have significant positive effect on lecturers productivity in government colleges of education in Kogi State, Nigeria. Yakubu, Bello, Yahaya and Adamu (2022) did an appraisal of the perception of staff on Tetfund's intervention in tertiary institutions in Adamawa State, Nigeria. The study adopted a study research design. From a population of 1,389 a sample of 311 was determined for the study. T-test statistic was used to verify the claims of the null hypotheses. Findings indicate that Tetfund intervention has significant and positive effect on academic staff training and development, academic research, physical infrastructure, modern instructional facilities and library collections development in the institutions being studied. The study concludes that Tetfund interventions have sustained real teaching and learning in the institutions studied.

Gap in Literature

The study examines the effect of Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) on development of higher education in Nigeria, in the areas of academic staff training and development, provision of instructional materials and equipment, research and publication as well as library collections development. No doubt many studies have been carried out in this area but to the best of our knowledge, we have not come across any study that examined the effect of TETFund's intervention on federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra State, that is, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Federal Polytechnic, Oko and College of Education (Technical), Umuze. The study is also different from others because none of the past studies have combined the mediating variables of the study in the manner we have done in the study. Besides, the gap can also be seen in the area of conflicting results emanating from past studies where some researchers/scholars found that TETFund's interventions have not made the required impact that can significantly affect tertiary education development in the country, against those who argued and concluded that TETFund's interventions have made significant impact in the tertiary education sector of Nigeria. For instance, this study has been necessitated among other things by the need for resolution of the conflicting reports in addition to finding out the factors that have militated against the agency in effectively delivering on its mandate.

For instance, Onyeike and Eseyin (2014), Onwuchekwa (2016) and Akomolafe and Bello (2019) were of the opinion that TETFund intervention have not been impactful, especially in the areas of academic staff training and development (AST&D), academic research and publication sponsorship. On the other hand, some researchers such as Ezekwe and Ani (2023), Isiaka, Nasiru and Olusola (2020) and Okolo, Adadu, Umma and Yamma (2021) among other scholars were of the opinion that TETFund has recorded milestone in many areas of intervention, including the construction and rehabilitation of physical infrastructure in Nigeria's tertiary institutions. The intention is to ascertain the collective as well as individual effects of the variables on the dependent variable, using the inferential statistics of correlation and multiple regression analysis.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study made use of descriptive survey design because the data was principally primary in nature and the result of the sample is generalized for the entire population of interest. The study adopted quantitative method of data analysis because quantitative data were collected. Both descriptive and inferential statistical tools were equally deployed in the analysis.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated to guide the objectives of the study as well as strengthen the analysis were re-stated and tested in this section of the analysis. Tests were conditioned at 0.05 level of significance.

Table 1: Correlation analysis

			Correlation Matrix					
Variables			TED	ASTD	IME	RSP	LCD	PHID
Tertiary Education Development	Pearson	Pearson	1	.501**	.621**	.593**	.637**	.491*
		Correlation		.000	.000	.000	.000	.001
		Sig. (2-tailed)	1106	.1106	.1106	.1106	.1106	.1106
N								
Academic staff Training and Development	Pearson	Pearson	.501**	1	.403*	.399*	.411*	.276*
		Correlation	.000		.000	.020	.010	.002
		Sig. (2-tailed)	1106	1106	.1106	.1106	.1106	.1106
N								
Instructional Materials and Equipment	Pearson	Pearson	.621**	.403*	1	.287*	.451*	.385*
		Correlation	.000	.000		.011	.001	.023
		Sig. (2-tailed)	1106	.1106	.1106	.1106	.1106	.1106
N								
Research and Publications	Pearson	Pearson	.593**	.399*	.287*	1	.283*	.284*
		Correlation	.000	.020	.003		.010	.003
		Sig. (2-tailed)	1106	.1106	.1106		.1106	.1106
N								
Library Collections Development	Pearson	Pearson	.637**	.411*	.451*	.283*	1	.397*
		Correlation	.000	.011	.001	.010		.002
		Sig. (2-tailed)	1106	.1106	.1106	.1106	.1106	.1106
N								
Physical Infrastructure Development	Pearson	Pearson	.551**	.339*	.528**	.467*	.307*	1
		Correlation	.000	.021	.001	.002	.013	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	1106	.1106	.1106	.1106	.1106	.1106
N								

** Correlation is significant at 0.05 level (2-tailed).

* Correlation is significant at 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation matrix between tertiary education development and proxies for independent variable showed there are strong positive relationship between them as well as positive but weak relationships among the proxies for independent variable in most cases. However, the correlation matrix did not present any conditions of multicollinearity or orthogonal relationships thereby showing that multiple regression analysis can be performed on the data.

Table 2: Summary of Analysis of Variance ANOVA for the Model

ANOVA ^b						
Source of Variation	df	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	F-ratio	Sig.	
Regression	4	311.791	77.948	20.616	.000 ^a	
Residual	120	453.685	3.781			
Total	124	765.476				

Predictor: (Constant), academic staff training and development, instructional materials and equipment, research publications, library collections development and physical infrastructure

Dependent Variable: Tertiary Education Development

The result of the analysis of variance (ANOVA) presented in Table 1 shows that the value of F-ratio is 20.616 and it is statistically significant because $p_{0.000}$ is less than 0.05 level of significance. Consequently, the model is considered valid and therefore fit for predictions.

. Table 3: Summary of Regression Results

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted Square	R-Standard of the Estimate	Error Durbin Watson Stat.
1	.560	.527	.401	.39057	2.017

a. predictor: (constant), academic staff training and development, instructional materials and equipment, research and publications and library collections development.

The summary of regression results presented in table 3 showed that regression coefficient represented in the table by ‘R’ with a value of .560 indicates that 56 percent relationship exists between the dependent variable (tertiary education development and the proxies for independent variable. Similarly the coefficient determination ‘R²’ otherwise, known as the explanatory of the model, with a value of .527 shows that 52.7 percent variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the proxies for independent variable. Also, the Durbin Watson Statistic of 2.017 is an indication that the data did not contain serial autocorrelation.

Table 4: Summary of Regression Coefficients, t-values and significance level

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sign
	β	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	-.176	.208	-	-.762	.443
Academic Staff training and development	.526	.046	.483	10.416	.000
Provision of instructional materials and equipment	.408	.057	.483	3.562	.000
Research and Publications	.472	.052	.521	2.073	.020
Library collection Development	.481	.073	.605	3.401	.011
Physical Infrastructure development	.501	.071	.771	2.609	.000

4. Dependent Variable: Tertiary Education Development

As could be seen from the table, variables’ weights are measured by their coefficients’ values. Therefore, it is easy to see the variable that contributes more to the development of the dependent variable. In other words, multiple regression analysis provides opportunity to measure the collective effect as well as the individual effect of the proxies for independent variable on the dependent variable. In other words, multiple regression analysis provides opportunity to measure the collective effect as well as the individual effect of the proxies for independent variable on the dependent variable. The result above equally showed that signs for the coefficients conformed to the a priori.

Hypotheses

The hypotheses formulated to guide the objectives of the study as well as strengthen the analysis were re-stated and tested in this section of the analysis. Tests were conditioned at 0.05 level of significance.

Re-statement of the study Hypotheses

1. H₀: Tetfund's intervention in academic staff training and development does not have significant and positive effect on tertiary education development in Federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra State.
H₁: Tetfund's intervention in academic staff training and development has significant and positive effect on tertiary education development in Federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra state.
2. H₀: Tetfund's intervention in provision of instructional materials and equipment does not have significant and positive effect on tertiary education development in Federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra State.
H₁: Tetfund's intervention in the provision of instructional materials and equipment does not have significant and positive effect on tertiary education development in Federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra state.
3. H₀: Tetfund's intervention in research and publications does not have significant and positive effect on tertiary education development in Federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra State.
H₁: Tetfund's intervention in research and publications has significant and positive effect on tertiary education development in Federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra state.
4. H₀: Tetfund's intervention in library collections development does not have significant and positive effect on tertiary education development in Federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra State.
H₁: Tetfund's intervention in library collections development has significant and positive effect on tertiary education development in Federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra state.
5. H₀: Tetfund's intervention in physical infrastructure development does not have significant and positive effect on tertiary educational institutional development in Anambra State.
H₁: Tetfund's intervention in physical infrastructure development has significant and positive effect on tertiary educational institutional development in Anambra State.

Interpretation of Regression Results

In this section of the analysis, we interpreted the regression results, using the coefficients of beta (β), t – value and other parameters in the model as follows:

As could be seen from table 4.10, the values of the proxies for the independent variable showed their relative weights on the dependent variable, using their coefficients as the measure of weight. Accordingly, coefficient of academic staff training and development (ASTD) represented in the model of α_1 , with a value of .509 in table 4.10 shows that if the variable is increased by one unit, tertiary education development will increase by 50.9 percent when other variables in the model are held constant. The t-value of 10.416 and its corresponding significance level of .000 are indications that the coefficient is significant because $P_{0.000}$ is less than $P < 0.05$. Consequent, the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative which suggests that Tetfund's intervention in academic staff training and development has significant and positive effect on tertiary educational institution in Anambra State was accepted.

In the same vein, the coefficient of provision of instructional materials and equipment represented by α_2 in the model with a value of .483 in table 4.10 means that when the variable is increased by one unit, the depend variable (tertiary education development) will increase by 48.3 percent when other variables in the model are held constant. Also, the t-value of 3.562 and the corresponding significance

level of .000 are indications that the coefficient is significant because $P_{0.000}$ is less than $P < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that Tetfund's intervention in the provision of instructional materials and equipment has significant and positive effect on tertiary education development in Federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra state.

Concerning the coefficient of provision for research and publication represented by α_3 in the model with a value of .521 in table 4.10, the implication is that if the variable is increased by one additional unit, tertiary education development will increase by 52.1 percent if other factors in the model are not allowed to vary. The t-value of 2.073 and its corresponding significance level of .020 are indications that the coefficient is significant because $P_{0.000}$ is less than $P < 0.05$. Consequently; the null hypothesis was rejected while the alternative in provision for research and publications has significant and positive effect on tertiary education development in federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra State.

As for the coefficient of library collections developments, the coefficient is represented in the model by α_4 with a value of .605 in table 4.10 and it means that when the variable is increased by one extra unit, tertiary education development will increase by 60.5 percent when other variables are held constant in the model. With a t-value of 3.401 and its corresponding significance level of .011, the coefficient is significant because $P_{0.011}$ is less than $P < 0.05$. This being the case, the null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that Tetfund's intervention in library collections development has significant and positive effect on tertiary education development in Federal Tertiary Education Development in Federal Tertiary educational institutions in Anambra state.

The coefficient of physical infrastructure development, represented by α_5 in the model with a coefficient of .771 in Table 4.10 means that when the variable is increased by one-unit, tertiary educational institution development will increase by 77.1 percent when other variables are held constant. The t-value of 2.609 and its corresponding significance level of .000 are indications that the coefficient is significant and positive because .000 is less than 0.05. Consequently, the null hypothesis was rejected and it was concluded that intervention in physical infrastructure development by Tetfund has significant and positive effect on Federal tertiary educational institutions development in Anambra State.

CONCLUSION

The study examined the effect of Tetfund's intervention on tertiary education development in Nigeria, using federal tertiary educational institutions in Anambra State as the study area. The findings of the study revealed that Tetfund's intervention on tertiary education development in Nigeria. Specifically, the study found that Tetfund's support for academic staff training and development, provision of instructional materials and equipment, research and publication and library collections development have all contributed to improved teaching, learning and research outcomes in Nigeria tertiary institutions.

The findings are consistent with the literature, which highlights the importance of investment in human capital, infrastructure and research in driving tertiary education development. The study's results also underscore the critical role that Tetfund has played and is still playing in supporting the development of tertiary education in Nigeria. Overall, the study provides evidence of the positive impact of Tetfund's intervention on tertiary education development in Nigeria and highlights the need for sustained investment in human capital, infrastructure, research, library collections development and physical infrastructure development to drive continued improvement in the sector.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and the conclusion drawn from them, the following recommendations were made:

1. TETfund's intervention in academic staff training and development (ASTD) towards tertiary education development is significant. However, there are many academics who have not

- benefited from the intervention for one reason or the other. We recommend that TETFund and the desk-officers across the public tertiary institution should relax its conditions for access to enable more academics benefit from the intervention.
2. TETFund's intervention in provision of instructional materials and equipment toward the enhancement of tertiary education is significant. However, there is room for improvement. TETFund should try and increase allocation for more provisions to increase impact.
 3. TETFund's intervention in research and publications is significant towards development of tertiary education. But as could be seen from the literature, many members of the teaching staff across the institutions under investigation have not benefited. We recommend that TETFund should expand coverage by increasing allocation to research and publications that more academics can have their manuscripts published.
 4. TETFund's intervention in library collections development is significant. But a lot still needs to be done. In order to enhance teaching, learning and research, more library collections are critical components. TETFund should do more in this area, especially with regard to e-library which are largely lacking in many tertiary institutions.
 5. TETFund's intervention in physical infrastructure development towards improvement in tertiary education is significant. Nevertheless, more physical infrastructure can be provided through the intervention fund. This can be achieved through more allocations to the institutions. Above all, we suggest that TETFund should establish a robust monitoring and evaluation unit to track the impact of its interventions and ensure that allocations are used for the purpose they were meant effectively.

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